

A Comparative Study of Selected Seed and Commercial Cocoon Markets

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Abstract

Silk is the outcome of various activities of Sericulture. The word sericulture is derived from the Greek word 'Sericos' meaning silk and the English word "culture" means rearing. Hence, sericulture can be defined as the cultivation or production of silk by rearing silkworms on large scale. Silkworm rearing is practiced by small, medium and large land holders and even landless farmers under rain fed and irrigated patterns. The present study is the outcome of 35 respondents who rear commercial and seed cocoons and sell them in respective markets; the primary data was collected using a model questionnaire by personal interview 23. Totally 11 important parameters like mulberry cultivated land area, mulberry varieties cultivated, manure and fertilizers use in mulberry cultivation, total number of dfls/layings reared in 1 batch, number of batches reared in 1 year, total yield of cocoon production per 100 dfls, maximum cost of 1Kg of cocoon, commonly reared breeds/hybrids by commercial farmer, commonly reared breeds/hybrids by seed farmer, bonus received for seed farmers along with the constraints/problems faced by the farmers were collected from 35 respondents. The results are presented in tabular and graphical forms and herein discussed.

Introduction

Silk is the most elegant textile in the world with unparalleled grandeur, natural sheen, and inherent affinity for dyes, high absorbance, light weight, soft touch and high durability and known as the "Queen of Textiles" the world over. Silk has been intermingled with the life and culture of the Indians. India has a rich and complex history in silk production and its silk trade dates back to 15th century. Sericulture industry provides employment to approximately 8 million persons in rural and semi-urban areas in India low capital intensive and highly remunerative nature. In recent years, sericulture has emerged as one of the potential enterprises for generating income at short intervals 6. It is an important agro based rural cottage industry, which covers the gamut of sericulture activities like mulberry cultivation, silkworm rearing, cocoon production, silk reeling and other post cocoon production stages. Due to the superiority of the end product, silk has been recognized as a natural textile fibre and as one of the high-value, low volume commodities to trade between the continents from time immemorial.

Sericulture is not new to India as references have been made in the epics of the Ramayana and Mahabharata. India has the unique distinction of being the only country producing all the five known commercial silks namely Mulberry, Tropical Tasar, Oak Tasar, Eri and Muga. India is the second largest producer of silk in the world¹⁸. The total annual silk production of India is 30348 MT, 21273 MT is produced by the Mulberry silkworm (bivoltine 5266 MT and cross breed 16007 MT) and Vanya (non-mulberry) silk of 9059 MT. Of which Eri silk- 5637 MT, Tasar- 3268 MT and Muga-170 MT with an export earnings of Rs. 528.60 crores (82 million US \$) from the sale of silk goods during 2017-18. Sericulture is one of the important sectors of economy in India which plays an important role in poverty alleviation. Compared to agricultural crops, sericulture provides more employment round the year and fetches higher income to the rural farm families⁹.

Market is a regular gathering of people for the purchase and sale of provisions, livestock, and other commodities. A cocoon market is a place where the buyers and sellers are required to transact cocoons by open auction under the regulations of law. The cocoon markets are established in Karnataka state by enforcing an act known as "The Karnataka silkworm Seed, Cocoon and Silk yarn (Regulation of Production, Supply, Distribution and Sale) Act 1959". The Cocoon markets of Karnataka are one of the best markets for the sale or purchase of cocoons. A series of prompt effort by the administrators has resulted in the highly organized dealing of cocoons has observed in the present day without affecting the rearers and reelers. There are at present 42 markets functioning throughout the state⁴.

The markets are of two types based on the type of cocoons that is transacted in seed cocoon and commercial cocoon markets. The transaction of bivoltine seed cocoons take place between the seed rearers on the one hand and licensed seed producers and government organization on the other hand. Popular bivoltine seed area markets are K.R. Pet, Hassan, Attibele & Anekal. The fixation of price to the bivoltine cocoons is by general assessment of the cocoons. The commercial cocoon markets are those markets where the cocoons used for reeling purpose are transacted. Here, the transaction is between the silkworm rearers and the reelers, government agencies also purchases cocoons here. These markets are classified as the Class I and Class II markets based on the quantity of cocoons transacted. There are 32 cocoon markets involved in the transaction of reeling cocoons in the state out of which 13 Class I and the remaining are Class II. Popular commercial cocoon markets are Kolar, Chikkaballapura, Ramanagara, Kollegala, T. Narasipura etc.

Methodology

The objectives of the present study is to compare and analyse different parameters between seed cocoon market and commercial cocoon market; To know the transaction details and activities in the market for a given period of time; To understand the socio-economic characters of seed rearers and commercial rearers. In the process of achieving the objectives of the study, it is very important to follow a systematic and scientific approach so as to present and interpret the results of the study or investigation conducted²³. The methodology outline, the features of the study area, the method of sampling and collection of data, the analytical frame work employed and the concepts are defined and explained to facilitate a clear understanding of the issues related to the present study.

Ramanagara district lies between North latitude 12o 24' and 13o 09' and East longitudes 77o 06' and 77o 34' E. Ramanagara district is located in the southern part of Karnataka. Ramangara city is the center of Sericulture activities with more than 2000 silk reeling and twisting household units. It is also one of the major cocoon markets in Asia. Krishnarajpet, also spelt as Krushnarajapete, is a Town Municipality Council and Taluk (Sub-District) in Mandya District in the South India state of Karnataka. Krishnarajpet district lies between North latitude 12.66° and East longitudes 76.49°. Krishnarajpet Town is located in Mandya district in the state of Karnataka in India.

Sampling Procedure and Source of data

The Sericulturists numbering 35 each from two types of farmers viz. commercial and seed cocoon rearers were interviewed personally by using a prepared questionnaire. Primary data pertaining to Sericulturists on socio-economic characteristics, land holdings, cropping pattern, asset position, cost and returns, marketing of cocoons and constraints involved in production of mulberry and silk cocoon were collected. Keeping in view the objectives of the study, the data pertaining to 2017-18 period were collected from the respondents during the months February-March, 2018. The secondary data relating to production of silk cocoon, market transaction details and market activities were collected from the market in-charge of selected cocoons markets and also from various other published sources. The primary data collected from 70 respondent farmers was subjected to simple tabular analysis. Tabular analysis including the computation of means, percentages etc., were employed to present the data in respect to demographic feature, socio-economic profile and cropping pattern adopted by sericulture farmers. The different parameters were calculated using following formula:

$$\text{Total percentage of respondent} = \frac{\text{Total no. of respondents}}{\text{No. of respondents}} \times 100$$

Results

The necessary data pertaining to **“Comparative study on seed and commercial cocoon markets”** were collected from the respondents of Ramanagara cocoon market (commercial) and Krishnarajpet cocoon market (bivoltine seed). The data were subjected to various statistical tools and techniques to draw informative conclusions, the results of the study are presented under the following sub-headings:

1. Mulberry cultivated land area
2. Mulberry varieties cultivated
3. Manure and fertilizers use in mulberry cultivation
4. Total number of dfls/layings reared in 1 batch
5. Number of batches reared in 1 year
6. Total yield of cocoon production per 100 dfls
7. Maximum cost of 1 Kg of cocoon
8. Commonly reared breeds/hybrids by commercial farmer
9. Commonly reared breeds/hybrids by seed farmer
10. Bonus received for seed farmers
11. Constraints/problems faced by the farmers

Table and Graph 1: Mulberry Cultivated Land Area

Mulberry land area	No. of respondents			
	CF	%	SF	%
Less than 1 acre	5	14	7	20
1-2 acre	14	40	16	46
More than 2 acre	16	46	12	34
Total	35	100	35	100

Legend: CF = Commercial Farmer SF = Seed Farmer

Mulberry cultivated land area for both commercial and seed farmers is shown in **Table and Graph 1**. Total 35 respondents of commercial farmers shows that maximum of the respondents 16(46%) have mulberry cultivated land area of more than 2 acres, 14 (40%) respondents have mulberry cultivated area of 1-2 acres and 5(14%) respondents have mulberry cultivated area of less than 1 acre. Out of 35 respondents from seed farmers, majority of the respondents 16(46%) have mulberry cultivated area of 1-2 acres, 12(34%) respondents have mulberry cultivated area of more than 2 acres and 7(20%) respondents have mulberry cultivated area of less than 1 acre.

Table and Graph 2: Mulberry Varieties Cultivated

Variety	No. of respondents			
	CF	%	SF	%
V1	25	71	27	77
S36	6	17	5	14
Mysore local	2	6	2	6
M5	2	6	1	3
Total	35	100	35	100

The mulberry varieties cultivated by both commercial and seed farmers are shown in **Table and Graph 2**. Out of 35 respondents from commercial farmers, maximum of the respondents 25(71%) cultivated V1 variety, 6(17%) respondents cultivated S36, 2(6%) respondents cultivates Mysore local variety and 2(6%) cultivated M5 variety. From 35 respondents of seed farmers, majority of the respondents 27(77%) cultivated V1 variety, 5(14%) respondents cultivated S36 variety, 2(6%) respondents cultivates Mysore local variety and 1(3%) respondents cultivated M5 variety. In both the type of farmers we can see that the commonly cultivated mulberry variety is V1 and the least cultivated varieties are Mysore local and M5.

Table and Graph 3: Manure and Fertilizers used in Mulberry Cultivation

Inputs	No. of respondents			
	CF	%	SF	%
FYM	11	31	12	34
NPK	14	40	12	34
Urea	7	20	4	12
Urea potash	3	9	7	20
Total	35	31	35	34

Manure and fertilizers use in mulberry cultivation for both commercial and seed farmers are shown in **Table and Graph 3**. The total respondents of commercial farmers shows that majority 14(40%) respondents use NPK, 11(31%) respondents use FYM, 7(20%) use urea and 3(9%) use urea potash. Where as in seed farmers majority of the respondents 12(34%) use FYM and 12(34%) NPK, 7(20%) respondents use urea potash and 4(12%) respondents use urea.

Table and Graph 4: Total Number of dfls Reared in 1 batch

No. of dfls per batch	No. of respondents			
	CF	%	SF	%
50-100	3	9	5	14
100-150	5	14	7	20
150-200	8	23	12	34
200-250	13	37	8	23
250-300	6	17	3	9
Total	35	100	35	100

Total number of disease free layings reared in 1 batch for both commercial and seed farmers are shown in Table and Graph 4. Out of 35 respondents from commercial farmers, majority of the respondents 13(37%) rear 200-250 dfls in 1 batch, 8(23%) respondents rear 150-200 dfls in 1 batch, 6(17%) respondents rear 250-300 dfls in 1 batch, 5(14%) respondents rear 100-150 dfls in 1 batch, 3(9%) respondents rear 50-100 dfls in 1 batch. In seed farmers' total of 35 respondents shows that majority of the respondents 12(34%) rear 150-200 dfls in 1 batch, 8(23%) respondents' rear 200-250 dfls in 1 batch, 7(20%) respondents rear 100-150 dfls in 1 batch, 5(14%) respondents rear 50-100 dfls in 1 batch and 3(9%) rear 250-300 dfls in 1 batch.

Table and Graph 5: Number of Batches Reared in 1 Year

No. of batches/year	No. of respondents			
	CF	%	SF	%
1-2	3	9	2	6
3-4	11	31	8	23
5-6	17	49	16	45
7-8	4	11	9	25
Total	35	100	35	100

Table and Graph 5 shows the number of batches for both commercial and seed farmers reared in 1 year. In commercial farmers out of 35 respondents, most of the respondents 17(49%) reared 5-6 batches in 1 year, 11(31%) respondents reared 3-4 batches in 1 year, 4(11%) respondents reared 7-8 batches in 1 year and 3(9%) respondents reared 1-2 batches in 1 year. Out of 35 respondents from seed farmers, majority of the respondent 16(45%) reared 5-6 batches in 1 year, 9(25%) respondents reared 7-8 batches in 1 year, 8(23%) respondents reared 3-4 batches in 1 year and 2(6%) reared 1-2 batches in 1 year.

Table and Graph 6: Total Yield of Cocoon Production Per 100 dfls

Yield in Kgs	No. of respondents			
	CF	%	SF	%
51-60	4	11	7	20
61-70	6	14	12	34
71-80	8	23	7	20
81-90	13	37	6	14
90-100	6	14	3	9
Total	35	100	35	100

From Table and Graph 6 we can see the total yield of cocoon production per 100 dfls for both commercial and seed farmers. In commercial farmers out of 35 respondents, majority of the respondents 13(37%) produce 81-90 Kgs. of cocoons per 100 dfls, 8(23%) respondents produce 71-80 Kgs. of cocoons per 100 dfls, 6(14%) respondents produce 61-70 Kgs. of cocoons per 100 dfls, 6(14%) respondents produce 90-100 Kgs. of cocoons per 100 dfls and 4(11%) respondents produce 51-60 Kgs. of cocoons per 100 dfls. Out of 35 respondents from seed farmers, most of the respondents 12(34%) produce 61-70 Kgs. of cocoons per 100 dfls, 7(20%) respondents produce 71-80 Kgs. of cocoons per 100 dfls, 7(20%) respondents produce 51-60 Kgs. of cocoons per 100 dfls, 6(14%) respondents produce 81-90 Kgs. of cocoons per 100 dfls and 3(9%) respondents produce 90-100 Kgs. of cocoons per 100 dfls.

Table and Graph 7: Maximum Cost of 1 Kg of Cocoons

Maximum Amount (Rs.)	No. of respondents			
	CF	%	SF	%
300-400	5	14	-	0
400-500	9	26	-	0
500-600	11	31	3	9
600-700	7	20	4	11
700-800	3	9	6	17
800-900	-	0	10	29
900-1000	-	0	12	34
Total	35	100	35	100

For both commercial and seed farmers the maximum cost of 1 kg. of cocoons is shown in Table and Graph 7. Among commercial farmers out of 35 respondents, majority of the respondents 11(31%) get maximum amount of Rs. 500-600 for 1 kg of cocoons, 9(26%) respondents get maximum amount of Rs. 400-500 for 1 kg. of cocoons 7(20%) respondents get maximum amount of Rs. 600-700 for 1 kg. of cocoons and 5(14%) respondents get maximum amount of Rs.300-400 for 1 kg. of cocoons. Out of 35 respondents, most of the respondents 12(34%) get a maximum amount of Rs. 900-1000 for 1 kg. of cocoons, 10(29%) respondents get a maximum amount of Rs. 800-900 for 1 kg. of cocoons, 6(17%) respondents get a maximum amount of Rs. 700-800 for 1 kg. of cocoons, 4(11%) respondents get a maximum amount of Rs.600-700 for 1 kg. of cocoon, 3(9%) respondents get a maximum amount of Rs. 500-600 for 1 kg. of cocoons.

Table and Graph 8: Commonly reared breeds/hybrids for commercial farmer

Breeds/hybrids	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
CB Gold	11	31
PM × CSR2	9	26
CSR2 × CSR4	15	43
Total	35	100

The commonly reared breeds/hybrids by commercial farmer in the study area are shown in **Table and Graph 8**. Out of the total 35 respondents, most of the respondents 15(43%) rear CSR2 × CSR4, which is followed by CB Gold 11(31%) respondents and PM × CSR2 9(26%) respondents.

Table and Graph 9: Commonly Reared Breed/Hybrids for Bivoltine Seed Farmer

Breed/hybrid	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
CSR2	27	77
CSR2 × CSR4	8	23
Total	35	100

The Commonly reared breed/hybrid for bivoltine seed farmer in the study area is shown in **Table and Graph 9**. From the table and figure, we can see that majority of the respondents 27(77%) from seed farmers rear CSR2 and 8(23%) respondents rear CSR2 × CSR4.

Table and Graph 10: Bonus Received for Bivoltine Seed Farmers

Amount	No. of respondents	Percentage (%)
Rs.70	28	80
Rs.175 (reeling purpose)	7	20

On interview with bivoltine seed farmers at KR Pet, out of the total 35 respondents, 28(80%) received a bonus amount of Rs.70 per Kg for seed purpose. Whereas 7(20%) respondents received a bonus of Rs.175 per Kg as the cocoons are unfit for seed purpose and sent to reeling is presented in **Table and Graph 10**.

Constraints faced by the farmers in mulberry cultivation and silkworm rearing were assessed. The association between the personal and socio-economic characteristics of the farmers and the constraints faced by them in sericulture was also determined. The farmers expressed constraints in mulberry cultivation such as high labour wages, inadequate labour, inadequate irrigation facilities, high cost of manures and fertilizers, lack of guidance and lack of knowledge about mulberry diseases and pests. They also reported constraints viz., high cost of rearing room and equipment, lack of credit and subsidy, lack of manpower, difficulty in controlling silkworm diseases, lack of knowledge regarding physical conditions in rearing room and grading of cocoons, long distance of cocoon trading units and unremunerative rates for cocoons during silkworm rearing. The personal and socio-economic characters of the farmers such as caste, social participation and level of knowledge in sericulture were found to have a significant association with the constraints faced by them in sericulture⁸.

Table and Graph 11: Constraints/Problems Faced by the Farmers

Sl. No.	Particulars	No. of respondents	Rank
1	Lack of silkworm disease control measures.	4	3
2	Shortage and high rate of labour.	3	4
3	Lack of knowledge about the advanced method of silkworm rearing.	3	4
4	Fluctuation in cocoon price.	2	5
5	Inadequate market facilities.	3	4
6	Shortage of water supply.	6	1

7	Inadequate technical guidance by Ext. staffs.	4	3
8	Low quality of DFLs or Chawki worms.	5	2
9	Cocoon transportation problem.	3	4
10	Shortage of inputs received.	2	5

The responses of both the commercial and seed farmers regarding the constraints/problems faced are indicated in Table 11. The most serious constraints/problems faced by both types of farmers are shortage of water supply, which is ranked 1st and responded by 6 respondents. Low quality of dfls or chawki worms is ranked 2nd and responded by 5 respondents. Lack of silkworm disease control measures (4 respondents) and inadequate technical guidance by extension staffs (4 respondents) are ranked 3rd. Constraints such as shortage and high rate of labour (3 respondents), lack of knowledge about the advanced method of silkworm rearing (3 respondents), inadequate market facilities (3 respondents) and cocoon transportation problem (3 respondents) are ranked 4th.

Fluctuation in cocoon price (2 respondents) and shortage of inputs received (92 respondents) are ranked 5th.

Discussion

The results of the study on “A comparative study on commercial and seed cocoon market” are discussed below. Most of the commercial farmers have mulberry cultivated area of more than 2 acres followed by 1-2 acres; this is due to their high commercial productivity and capacity of rearing per batch/year. Whereas most of the seed farmers have mulberry cultivated land area of 1-2 acres followed by more than 2 acres, this is due to their lower productivity and less capacity of rearing per batch/year. Different varieties of mulberry have different protein, carbohydrates and moisture compositions, a good variety have all the optimum compositions. We can see that maximum of the respondents in both types of farmers cultivate V1 which is followed by S36. This is due to their higher nutrient compositions, high leaf yielding and easy acclimatization.

FYM and NPK are the most commonly use manure and fertilizers used in mulberry cultivation. This is due to their easy availability at low cost and effectiveness. The total number of dfls/layings reared in 1 batch is higher in commercial farmers, majority of the respondents are rearing 200-250 dfls/layings in 1 batch because they have bigger rearing house and larger mulberry cultivated land area. In seed farmers, majority of the respondents are rearing 150-200 dfls/layings in 1 batch. In both the commercial and seed farmers, most of the respondents are rearing 5-6 batches in a year followed by 3-4 batches and 7-8 batches. The number of batches reared in 1 year is mostly dependent of the availability of the host plant (mulberry) and demands from the markets. The total harvest is higher in commercial farmers than the seed farmers, majority of the commercial respondents harvested about 81-90 Kgs. per 100 dfls whereas most of the seed respondents harvested 60-70 Kgs. per 100 dfls. This is due to the direct procurement of chawki worms from CRCs by the commercial farmers which enhanced the effective rate of rearing (ERR).

Cost of cocoons varies for both the commercial and seed farmers as the criteria for price fixation is completely different in both the farmers. In some cases of seed farmers, where the criteria for seed purpose is not met they are sent for reeling purpose. Majority of the commercial farmers gets a maximum amount of Rs. 500-600 per Kg. and minimum amount of Rs.400-450 per Kg. whereas in seed farmers, majority of the respondents get a maximum amount of Rs.900-1000 per Kg. and minimum amount of Rs.500-600 per Kg. CSR2×CSR4 is the most commonly reared breeds/hybrids by the commercial farmers followed by CB Gold and PM×CSR2. CSR2 is the most commonly reared breed/hybrids for bivoltine seed farmer followed by CSR2×CSR4. Bonus for cocoon sale is given only to seed farmers, out of the total 35 seed farmer respondents, 28(80%) received a bonus amount of Rs.70 per Kg. for seed purpose. Whereas 7(20%) respondents received a bonus of Rs.175 per Kg. as the cocoons are unfit for seed purpose and are sent to reeling.

The constraints/problems faced by both commercial and seed farmers are highlighted below.

The most serious constraints/problems face by both types of farmers is shortage of water supply, due to water shortage and high temperature farmers faced difficulty to carry out the sericultural operations as they are labour intensive enterprise⁸. Low quality of dfls or chawki worms is also a major problem faced by the respondents as they faced low effective rate of rearing (ERR). Constraints such as lack of silkworm disease control measures, inadequate technical guidance by extension staffs, shortage and high rate of labour, lack of knowledge about the advanced method of silkworm rearing, inadequate market facilities and cocoon transportation problem are also another major constraints faced by the farmers. Fluctuation in cocoon price and shortage of inputs received are the least reported constraints/problems.

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